

Steering the Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂-to-SrTiO₃ hydrothermal transformation for controlling the functionality of two-dimensional (2D) SrTiO₃ nanoplatelets for photocatalytic H₂ evolution

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ABSTRACT

The Aurivillius-Phase Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ platelets are not only important functional materials in their own right, but also serve as valuable two-dimensional (2D) templates for converting into 2D ATiO₃ (A = Sr, Ba, Ca) perovskite platelets with a favourable (100) orientation. The transformation under low-temperature (200 °C) hydrothermal conditions has recently been demonstrated; however, the process remains underexplored regarding the mechanistic control of the final product properties. This study sheds light on the steering of the Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂-to-SrTiO₃ hydrothermal transformation to precisely control the surface roughness and photocatalytic properties of the 2D epitaxial heterostructural SrTiO₃/Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ and SrTiO₃ nanoplatelets. A higher excess of Sr (Sr/Ti = 15), smaller Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ template nanoplatelets, and pre-reaction etching of the template with hot NaOH promote the formation of high-surface-area SrTiO₃/Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ and SrTiO₃ nanoplatelets (BET >60 m²/g), which show more than 50 times higher H₂ evolution rates compared to smooth, low surface area platelets (BET~10 m²/g). This study demonstrated that higher surface roughness facilitates effective surface trapping of bismuth species, which, through in-situ reduction to metallic Bi⁰ single atoms, acted as a co-catalyst and enhanced photocatalytic H₂ evolution. Both SrTiO₃/Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ and SrTiO₃ nanoplatelets exhibited stable photocatalytic responses, but only SrTiO₃ maintained structural and chemical integrity under illumination. This study presents a new strategy for engineering the surface and functional properties of 2D SrTiO₃ perovskite nanoplatelets through the hydrothermal transformation of Aurivillius phase Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ nanoplatelets, thereby expanding possibilities for the functional engineering of other 2D perovskite nanostructures.

1. Introduction

Science and technology face significant expectations in the race to tackle global challenges related to climate change, pollution, and the depletion of energy resources. Part of the scientific efforts focus on utilising solar energy to produce alternative fuels and degrade organic pollutants. Over the past 15 years, hydrogen (H₂) fuel produced using sunlight has gained considerable attention as a promising pathway towards a low-carbon future. Among the various solar-driven methods for H₂ production (photoelectrochemical, photovoltaic-electrochemical approaches, etc.), the photocatalytic process stands out for its

simplicity, low cost, and suitability for scaling up [1]. However, several challenges remain unresolved, including low sunlight conversion efficiency, limited photocatalyst stability, and the need for effective separation of hydrogen (H₂) and oxygen (O₂). These issues persist despite extensive research efforts, hindering the commercialisation of this promising technology [2,3].

Given the vast number of photocatalytic studies conducted over the last 20 years, it is evident that the breakthrough in the practical exploitation of the photocatalytic processes cannot occur through serendipitous photocatalyst discovery alone, but must arise from knowledge-driven design. Architectures such as 2D/2D epitaxial

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heterojunctions with direct Z-scheme charge transfer, combined with single-atom co-catalysts, represent state-of-the-art approaches that can simultaneously overcome several bottlenecks in photocatalytic performance [4,5]. The rational design of 2D nanostructures and 2D/2D epitaxial heterostructures can be achieved by converting suitable 2D template precursors under low-temperature hydrothermal conditions that promote dissolution-mediated epitaxial reconstruction. The choice of 2D templates is generally limited to nanostructures that naturally tend to grow anisotropically, a property influenced by their crystal structure. Layered crystal structures, distinguished by the exchange of various structural units, are among the most favourable templates for transforming into new 2D or 2D/2D materials. Besides structural compatibility with the target material, the success of the transformation also relies on the relative solubilities and stabilities of all participating structures under the given conditions [6–9].

Aurivillius phases ($(\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2)(\text{A}_{n-1}\text{B}_n\text{O}_{3n+1})$) exemplify spontaneously forming layered 2D (nano)structures, where pseudo-perovskite blocks exchange with $(\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2)^{2+}$ layers [10]. These 2D materials have been extensively studied for preparing 2D perovskite platelets through topochemical transformation [11–14]. $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$, composed of alternating $(\text{Bi}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{10})^{2-}$ blocks and $(\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2)^{2+}$ layers, is an example of the Aurivillius phase. Due to this layered structure, it naturally grows in anisotropic shapes of (nano)platelets [15–18]. Thanks to this specific crystal structure and the favourable topochemical transformation chemistries in different reaction media, $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ (nano)platelets also provide versatile opportunities for engineering 2D ATiO_3 ($\text{A} = \text{Ba}, \text{Sr}, \text{Ca}$) perovskites. Until recently, this type of transformation was mainly studied in molten salt media [10–14]. Our group first reported the transformation of $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ nanoplatelets into $\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ heterostructures and SrTiO_3 nanoplatelets under low-temperature hydrothermal conditions [6,7,19]. Following our example, but with an innovative modification involving the addition of sodium oleate—which significantly altered the conversion mechanism—Wu et al. also prepared BaTiO_3 and $\text{Ba}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{TiO}_3$ platelets through the hydrothermal transformation of $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ platelets [20–22].

Despite a relatively large band gap of 3.2 eV, which limits the use of only the ultraviolet part of the solar spectrum (just 5%), SrTiO_3 has been widely researched as a photocatalyst for H_2 evolution, mainly because of its low cost and photo-corrosion stability. The highest quantum efficiency of nearly 1 and the largest scale-up of sunlight-driven H_2 generation were achieved precisely by cube-like Al-doped SrTiO_3 particles loaded with $\text{Rh}/\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ and CoOOH cocatalysts [2,3]. These studies support further research into SrTiO_3 nanostructures in the field of photocatalytic H_2 evolution, especially those with more optimal 2D nanostructures, which are of significant interest.

Continuing our previous investigations on the hydrothermal $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ -to- SrTiO_3 transformation, this work provides the first evidence that the transformation pathway can be intentionally steered to tailor the morphology, surface area, and functional properties of the transformed 2D/2D $\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ and 2D SrTiO_3 nanostructures. We present two distinct experimental strategies that yielded significant differences in surface roughness and, correspondingly, in their contrasting photocatalytic performances. We demonstrated that rough, high surface-area SrTiO_3 nanoplatelets derived from $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ efficiently expose a small amount of remaining bismuth nanospecies at their surfaces, which can be in-situ photo-reduced into metallic Bi^0 single atoms, acting as efficient non-noble metal co-catalysts for H_2 evolution.

Moreover, our results emphasise the importance of a thorough understanding and precise control of the synthesis process in the development of nanostructured materials with reproducible and tunable functionalities. This study is not only important for the advancement of SrTiO_3 -based photocatalysis, but also contributes significantly to the rational design of 2D nanostructures and 2D/2D epitaxial heterostructures through low-temperature hydrothermal topochemical transformation.

2. Experimental

2.1. Synthesis conditions

2.1.1. Chemicals

All chemicals were used as received without further purification. KCl (Sigma-Aldrich, $\geq 99.0\%$), NaCl (Merck, $\geq 99.7\%$), Bi_2O_3 nanopowder (Alfa Aesar, 99.8%), TiO_2 (P25, Degussa), $\text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Sigma-Aldrich, $\geq 99.0\%$), NaOH (Fisher Chemicals, $\geq 98.7\%$), HNO_3 (VWR, 68%). The water, that we used in the synthesis processes, was purified with a system to produce 18.2 M Ω .cm ultra-pure water (Purelab Option-Q7, ELGA).

2.1.2. Synthesis of the $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ template nanoplatelets

The $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ template platelets were synthesised using the molten salt method, as described in our previous reports [6,7,11,12,19]. In brief, we thoroughly mixed TiO_2 and Bi_2O_3 nanopowders with NaCl and KCl salts in the molar ratio of $\text{NaCl}:\text{KCl}:\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3:\text{TiO}_2 = 50:50:2:3$. The powder mixture was placed in an Al_2O_3 crucible, covered, and heated above the salts' melting temperature using three different temperature programmes. The purpose of employing different heating regimes was to produce $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ platelets with varying size distributions. The first programme involved heating at a rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, followed by a 2-hour annealing at this temperature, then cooling at $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to room temperature. This process is referred to as $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/2\text{ h}$ (see Table S1 and Table S2). A similar process with a shorter 1-hour anneal was labelled $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/1\text{ h}$. The third annealing programme included heating at $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, cooling at $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, holding for 2 h at this temperature, then reheating at $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and finally slowly cooling at $1\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, followed by uncontrolled cooling to room temperature. This sequence is abbreviated as $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}-700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/2\text{ h}-800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (see Table S2). After each heating cycle, reaction products were separated from the salts by dissolving the salts in water. The resulting powders were then soaked in 2 M HNO_3 for 10 min to remove any residual secondary phases. The powders were repeatedly washed with water to eliminate any remaining HNO_3 . The pure $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ platelets were obtained after freeze-drying.

2.1.3. Hydrothermal transformation of the $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ template nanoplatelets into heterostructural $\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ and SrTiO_3 nanoplatelets

The hydrothermal topochemical conversion process from our previous reports was further examined to explore different experimental conditions for adjusting the functional properties [6,7,19]. In the present study, the hydrothermal transformation was performed using two different, carefully controlled procedures, Procedure 1 and Procedure 2. In the initial stage, which was similar for both procedures, $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ platelets and $\text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were mixed with a small amount of water, necessary for dissolving the salt. The suspension was sonicated for 20 min, after which it was transferred to the PTFE insert, and the residue was washed with a minimal amount of water. NaOH solution was prepared separately in a flask. Although the procedures differed in the concentrations and temperatures of the initially added NaOH, the final NaOH concentration in the autoclave was the same (6 M). The concentrations of all reagents in the autoclaves, together with other data (Sr/Ti ratios, size of the $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ template nanoplatelets), are summarised in Table S1 and Table S2. The main differences between the procedures are described as follows. In Procedure 1, all reagents were cooled to room temperature before being combined. The initial NaOH solution prepared was less concentrated (6.2 mol/l), and only a few millilitres of water were needed to fill 70% of the autoclave volume. The heating process began immediately after mixing the reagents and sealing the autoclave. Procedure 2 relies on the natural formation of hot NaOH during the exothermic dissolution of NaOH in water. This hot and concentrated NaOH (12 M) was then poured over the dispersion of the $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ nanoplatelets in SrCl_2 water solution. A certain amount

(approximately 220 ml) of water was added to achieve the target 70 % filling of the autoclave (total PTFE insert volume: 700 ml). At this stage, immediately after mixing the reagents, the suspension temperature was typically 46 °C–48 °C. The start of heating to the target reaction temperature (i.e., 200 °C) was delayed for approximately 30 min to prolong the etching effect of warm NaOH. During this period, the suspension cooled to approximately 32 °C–34 °C. The reactions were conducted under stirring conditions (150 rpm) in a Teflon-lined autoclave (BR 700), with heating to the final temperature taking about 2 h, while the reaction time at 200 °C varied from 2.5 to 24 h (see Tables S1 and S2). After cooling the reactor to room temperature, the powder was separated from the alkaline solution by centrifugation. Subsequently, soluble species (Na^+ , Cl^- , OH^- , Sr^{2+}) were removed from the reaction product through repeated water washing and centrifugation. Water-insoluble side products, SrCO_3 and Bi_2O_3 , were dissolved using 1 M HNO_3 (soaking for 5 min). The perovskite platelets were then immediately separated from the acid, followed by water washing to remove residual acid. Non-aggregated, well-separated $\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ or SrTiO_3 platelets were obtained after freeze-drying.

2.2. Characterisation

2.2.1. Structural, morphological, surface and electrochemical characterisation

The crystal structure of the synthesised materials was determined using X-ray diffractometers Bruker AXS D4 Endeavour and Empyrean, Malvern PANalytical, both with $\text{CuK}\alpha_1$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was conducted on powder samples (randomly oriented platelets) as well as on the oriented platelets on the zero-background Si single-crystalline substrate. The latter samples were prepared by casting droplets of the well-sonicated suspension of the platelets in 2-propanol onto the Si single-crystalline substrate. This method was employed for the quantitative determination of the $\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ ratio in the heterostructures via a calibration curve obtained from XRD measurements of the oriented platelets with known ratios of SrTiO_3 and $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$. The selected diffraction lines for quantification were (100), (200) for SrTiO_3 and (008), (0014) for $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$.

The microstructural analyses were carried out using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Schottky FEG, Verios HP 4G, Thermofisher, USA). Scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) analyses were performed on aberration-corrected microscope ARM 200 CF (Jeol, Japan) operated at 200 kV and equipped with cold field emission gun (FEG) and energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) detector. Bright-field (BF-STEM) and high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF-STEM) images were acquired on an annular detector with inner and outer semi-angles of 11–22 mrad and 68–180 mrad, respectively. For EDX mapping of Bi nanoparticles in SrTiO_3 matrix, we used aberration-corrected microscope Spectra 300 (Thermo Fisher, Netherlands) with high-brightness FEG and operated at 200 kV. The microscope is equipped with four 30 mm² windowless collimated silicon drift detectors (SDDs) with large 0.7 sr solid angle (Super-X EDXS detector) for fast and precise elemental analysis. For STEM analyses of the platelets in top-view orientation, the samples were dispersed in absolute ethanol and applied onto lacey carbon coated copper grids. For analysis of the platelets in edge-view, the samples were embedded in epoxy resin and thinned to electron transparency by mechanical and ion milling (Gatan PIPS Model 691, USA).

X-ray photo-electron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were performed using PHI Versaprobe III with $\text{Al K}\alpha$ radiation at 1486.6 eV. The acquired data was analysed using Multipak software (PHI) while using C1s peak at 284.8 eV as the reference. The photocatalysts after the photocatalytic process were analysed by ex-situ XPS to determine the light-induced changes in the surface elements' chemical states. To preserve the elements' oxidation states, the powders were first separated from the photocatalytic solution under an argon atmosphere, dried under vacuum and then deposited on the XPS sample holder under a

nitrogen atmosphere (in dry box). Using this procedure, we tried to avoid the air exposure of the sample after the photocatalytic process. The powders' Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) surface areas were determined by nitrogen adsorption with a Micromeritics Gemini II 2370 nitrogen-adsorption apparatus (Norcross, GA).

The diffuse reflectance spectra of the platelets were measured in the ultraviolet and visible (UV–Vis) spectral range using a spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-3600, Tokyo, Japan) equipped with an integrating sphere containing BaSO_4 as the standard. The band gap energies were determined from the diffuse reflectance spectra by means of the Tauc method and the Kubelka-Munk function [23].

For photo-electrochemical measurements, a 5 mm L-shaped glassy carbon electrode was used as the working electrode, onto which a catalyst layer was deposited. To prepare the catalyst ink, 3 mg of powdered catalyst was dispersed in a mixed solvent containing 0.75 mL of deionized water, 0.25 mL of 2-propanol, and 10 μL of Nafion, followed by ultrasonic treatment to ensure uniform dispersion. This ink was then drop-casted onto the glassy carbon surface at a loading of 0.3 mg/cm². The electrochemical setup also included a graphite rod as the counter electrode and a Mini-HydroFlex reversible hydrogen electrode (Gaskatel) as the reference electrode. A quartz cube reactor, filled with approximately 100 mL of 1 M KOH electrolyte and purged with nitrogen, housed the electrodes. The catalyst surface was illuminated by a 300 W xenon lamp (Newport) equipped with an AM1.5G filter, calibrated to simulate 1 sun (100 mW/cm²) using a silicon reference cell (Newport). All electrochemical measurements were conducted under illumination using a Gamry 1010E potentiostat. Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) was performed within the range of 0 to –0.8 V (vs RHE) at a scan rate of 2 mV/s, while electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was carried out at a potential of –0.5 V (vs RHE), spanning frequencies from 100 kHz to 1 MHz. Mott Schottky (MS) measurements were performed at a frequency of 1 kHz for all the samples.

2.2.2. Photocatalytic H₂ production test

The photocatalytic H₂ evolution reactions were carried out in a 73-mL quartz photoreactor (23-mL headspace) with an airtight rubber septum at the top and maintained at room temperature (RT). Typically, 20 mg of photocatalyst was suspended in 50 mL of aqueous solution containing 25 % methanol (v/v), which served as a hole scavenger, and the suspension was sonicated for 30 min to obtain a well-dispersed particle suspension. This mixture was sealed in a quartz round bottom flask with rubber septum and purged with N₂ gas for 30 min to remove excess oxygen in the reaction mixture. Finally, the sealed flask was illuminated with light for 4 h (Fig. S1). A 300 W Xenon arc lamp (Newport) equipped with an AM 1.5G filter was used to simulate solar irradiation. The irradiance at the sample surface was measured with a calibrated optical power meter (Newport) and found to be 100 mW·cm^{–2}, corresponding to the standard AM 1.5G solar intensity. The spectrum of the Xe lamp with the AM 1.5G filter is also provided, as shown in Fig. S2. Gas products were sampled hourly with a gas-tight syringe to analyse the H₂ content using a gas chromatograph (GC, SRI–8610C) with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD); high-purity nitrogen was used as the carrier gas. The calibration of the GC is described in Supplementary Material (Fig. S3).

The apparent quantum efficiency (AQE) of the reactions was calculated according to the following equation:

$$\text{AQE (\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of reacted electrons}}{\text{Number of incident photons}} \times 100$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural, microstructural and morphological characterisation

The three varieties of $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ template nanoplatelets, intended for hydrothermal transformation into heterostructural $\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$

Table I

List of the studied SrTiO₃ (STO) and SrTiO₃/Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ (STO/BIT) nanoplatelets together with the summary of the experimental synthesis conditions, composition and BET specific surface areas. Denotations Procedure 1 and Procedure 2 refer to two sets of hydrothermal experiments, as described in Section 2.1.3 (Tables S1, S2).

Sample denotation	Synthesised platelet material (template BIT platelet average side length (L))	Hydrothermal conditions (Sr/Ti, C _{NaOH} (mol/l), T/time)	STO/BIT weight ratio	BET (m ² /g)
Procedure 1				
C1	STO/BIT (1.4 μm)	12, 6 M NaOH, 200 °C/2.5 h	0.8/1	6
C2	STO/BIT (1.4 μm)	12, 6 M NaOH, 200 °C/6 h	1.2/1	10
C3	STO (1.4 μm)	12, 6 M NaOH, 200 °C/15 h	SrTiO ₃	11
C4	STO (1 μm)	15, 6 M NaOH, 200 °C/20 h	SrTiO ₃	26
Procedure 2				
H1	STO/BIT (1.4 μm)	15, 6 M NaOH, 200 °C/18 h	0.9/1	39
H2	STO/BIT (1 μm)	15, 6 M NaOH, 200 °C/15 h	1/1	64
H3	STO (1 μm)	15, 6 M NaOH, 200 °C/24 h	SrTiO ₃	61
H4	STO/BIT (0.9 μm)	15, 6 M NaOH, 200 °C/18 h	1.3/1	53

and SrTiO₃ nanoplatelets, were synthesised under different molten salt (NaCl/KCl) conditions. All three Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ nanoplatelet types were discrete, well separated, and highly crystalline, exhibiting an orthorhombic crystal structure (space group: B2ab). Variations in their side length distribution resulted from different annealing regimes (Detailed description in Section S1, Figs. S4, S5).

Under highly alkaline (6 M NaOH) conditions combined with a high strontium excess (Sr/Ti = 12–15), the Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂-to-SrTiO₃ transformation proceeds via Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ dissolution and SrTiO₃ epitaxial growth over both basal surface planes of the template platelets, as described in great detail in our previous reports and summarised in Section S2 of Supplementary Material [6,7,24]. Due to the epitaxial growth mechanism, a highly ordered epitaxial interface forms between the SrTiO₃ and Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ along the platelets' basal surface planes, as

shown in Fig. S6. The transformation mechanism was found to be highly reproducible, although the surface roughness of the growing SrTiO₃ varied considerably, depending on strontium excess, template size and quality, and pre-reaction exposure to warm alkaline conditions. The correlations between these experimental parameters and the surface roughness of the forming SrTiO₃ were evaluated through eight representative examples, as shown in Table I. The first set of experiments (Procedure 1, samples C1-C4) used cold NaOH solutions (R.T.), while in the second set (Procedure 2, samples H1-H4), the template platelets were subjected to hot NaOH/Sr(OH)₂ etching for 30 min before being heated to a target temperature of 200 °C. In both experimental series, the aim was to prepare heterostructural nanoplatelets with a SrTiO₃:Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ weight ratio close to 1:1 as well as pure SrTiO₃ nanoplatelets. Regardless of the procedure, the orientation of the growing SrTiO₃ was (100), as dictated by the (00l) orientation of the Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ nanoplatelets. XRD patterns revealed similar diffraction line widths for SrTiO₃, irrespective of the experimental conditions (Fig. 1 and Fig. S7).

The most notable differences among the samples were observed in surface roughness. Smooth surface platelets are typically formed in Procedure 1, using larger templates and lower strontium excess (Table I). In contrast, smaller templates combined with higher strontium excess (Sr/Ti = 15), especially in Procedure 2, favoured the formation of rough basal surfaces of formed platelets. Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show both morphological types of heterostructural and SrTiO₃ nanoplatelets, respectively, as seen from SEM and STEM micrographs. Variations in surface roughness were reflected in the BET specific surface area values (Table I). Additional details on structural/morphological analysis, as well as Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂-to-SrTiO₃ transformation rates under different experimental conditions (side length, Sr/Ti, procedure type) are provided together with the SEM images of all studied samples (Figs. S8 and S9) in the Section S3 Supplementary Information. The porous rough surface of SrTiO₃, in some respects, resembles the TiO₂ nanobelts or TiO₂ nanoparticles with nanocavities, which were also studied as photocatalysts [25–28] or for electrochemical lithium storage [29]. The reported nanocavities in TiO₂ nanostructures do not form in the process of epitaxial growth, as is the case with SrTiO₃ in our study. The formation of nanocavities in TiO₂ nanobelts was attributed to the removal of water and surface dehydroxylation during annealing of H₂Ti₃O₇ nanobelts, while the nanocavities in TiO₂ nanoparticles were correlated with the incorporation of fluorine in the TiO₂ lattice during microwave-assisted hydrolysis and post-annealing.

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of the preferentially oriented SrTiO₃/Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ and SrTiO₃ nanoplatelets (cast on a single-crystalline silicon substrate) synthesised in 6 M NaOH at 200 °C after using different experimental conditions (Table I), as detailed in Experimental Section 2.1.3 in Table S1 (a) and Table S2 (b). As evident from the XRD patterns of the samples denoted by C3, C4, and H3, these are pure SrTiO₃, while those marked with C1, C2, H1, H2 and H4 are SrTiO₃/Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ heterostructures. For the indexing of the diffraction patterns, the JCPDS reference cards 01-074-1296 and 01-083-8385 were used for SrTiO₃ and Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂, respectively.

Fig. 2. (a, e) SEM and (b, c, f, g) STEM micrographs of the representative $\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ platelets, synthesised by Procedure 1 (a-c: Sample C1 in Table 1) and by Procedure 2 (e-g: Sample H2 in Table 1). The $\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ platelets, denoted as sample C1 and sample H2 were prepared from the $\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ template platelets with the average side length (L) of 1.4 μm and 1 μm , respectively. The Sr/Ti initial molar ratios were 12 and 15 for the samples C1 and H2, respectively. In both cases, $C_{\text{NaOH}} = 6 \text{ M}$ and $T = 200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, while the reaction time was 2.5 h for sample C1 (a-c) and 15 h for sample H2 (e-g). (d, h) Schematic presentation of the main difference between the two types of platelets in terms of their surface roughness.

3.2. Surface characterisation by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

Photocatalytic reactions are surface-controlled processes; therefore, surface characterisation techniques like XPS are vital for clarifying the link between surface chemistry and photocatalytic behaviour. In this study, XPS was used to examine the surface chemical states of the elements constituting the platelets—strontium, titanium, oxygen, and bismuth—both before and after the photocatalytic assessment. It is important to highlight that in this case, the XPS results are not suitable

for reliable quantitative analysis of the composition due to the different surface roughness and particular shape of cleaved platelets. Nonetheless, these measurements offer valuable insights into the surface characteristics relevant to the photocatalytic process. The XPS survey scans confirmed the presence of Sr, Ti, O, and Bi in all the as-prepared heterostructural $\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ and SrTiO_3 platelets. With the exception of C, no other foreign element was detected (Fig. S10). Fig. 4 shows the high-resolution XPS spectra for representative heterostructures (Fig. 4a) and pure SrTiO_3 nanoplatelets (Fig. 4b). Regardless of the degree of

Fig. 3. (a, e) SEM and (b, c, f, g) STEM micrographs of the representative SrTiO₃ platelets, synthesised by Procedure 1 (a-c: Sample C3 in Table I) and Procedure 2 (e-g: Sample H3 in Table I). SrTiO₃ platelets, denoted as sample C3 and sample H3 were prepared from the Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ template platelets with an average side length of 1.4 μm and 1 μm, respectively. The Sr/Ti initial molar ratios were 12 and 15 for the samples C3 and H3, respectively. In both cases, C_{NaOH} = 6 M and T = 200 °C, while the reaction time was 15 h for sample C3 (a-c) and 24 h for sample H3 (e-g). (d, h) Schematic presentation of the platelets, completely transformed to SrTiO₃ prepared according to the two different procedures, which show significantly different surface roughness that reflects in the difference in BET (Table I).

transformation, Sr 3d XPS spectra of heterostructures and SrTiO₃ show peaks at 132.6 eV and 134.4 eV, corresponding to Sr 3d_{5/2} and Sr 3d_{3/2} states, thus confirming the bonding of Sr²⁺ in SrTiO₃. Similarly, the binding energies of Ti 2p_{3/2} at 458.2 eV and Ti 2p_{1/2} at 464.0 eV indicate the Ti⁴⁺ oxidation state. The detection of bismuth in SrTiO₃ platelets by XPS confirms that during the conversion process, captured and trapped bismuth species are present on or near the surface. The highest intensities of Bi 4f states, appearing at a binding energy of 159.0 eV (Bi 4f_{7/2}) and 164.0 eV (Bi 4f_{5/2}), correspond to Bi³⁺ bonded to oxygen. The asymmetry of the Bi 4f peaks demonstrates the presence of metallic Bi⁰. Obvious shoulder peaks, observed at 157 eV and 162.3 eV in the Bi 4f spectra of the rough surface SrTiO₃ (Sample H3) and SrTiO₃/Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂

(Sample H2) platelets, indicate higher initial Bi⁰ content at the surface of these platelets compared to those with smooth surfaces and lower BET values (Samples C2, C3 and C4).

3.3. Photocatalytic activity evaluation and stability

The significant contrast in the surface roughness of the platelets initiated an investigation to clarify how these variations influence photocatalytic properties. Several key features, such as the formation of a large contact area in the SrTiO₃/Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ epitaxial heterojunction, surface-trapped bismuth species, and the reported band structure properties of SrTiO₃, motivated the assessment of the developed

Fig. 4. Comparison of the representative XPS spectra of the as-prepared (a) $\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ and (b) SrTiO_3 nanoplatelets prepared by Procedure 1 (Samples C2, C3, C4) and Procedure 2 (Samples H2 and H3) (Table 1).

Fig. 5. (a) Rate of H_2 evolution over the $\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ (samples C1, C2, H1, H2 and H4) and SrTiO_3 (samples C3, C4 and H3) nanoplatelets, prepared by Procedure 1 (C1-C4 (violet columns)) and Procedure 2 (H1-H4 (red columns)), (b, c) stability test of H_2 evolution: (b) for $\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ platelets (Sample H2) and (c) for SrTiO_3 platelets (Sample H3). Every 4 h reaction, the formed H_2 was evacuated. Photocatalytic experiments were performed for the suspension of photocatalysts (20 mg) in a 50 ml aqueous solution containing 25 vol% of methanol.

nano-platelets for photocatalytic H_2 evolution. Band gap (E_g) determination from UV-VIS diffuse reflectance spectra using the Tauc method and the Kubelka-Munk function [23] revealed no significant difference between the E_g of the heterostructural platelets and that of the SrTiO_3 platelets obtained by the two procedures. The E_g values varied between 3.22 eV and 3.28 eV, as presented in Fig. S11. A Detailed description of the band gap determination is also given in the Supplementary Material. The results of the photocatalytic measurements, shown in Fig. 5 and summarised in Table S3 (Extended Table data of Table 1), disclosed significant variation in H_2 evolution rates. No direct correlation was observed between photocatalytic activity and platelet composition. Both pure SrTiO_3 platelets and $\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ platelets demonstrated either high or low H_2 evolution rates. A general observation is that platelets with a smooth surface and BET surface area below $12 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ displayed considerably lower photocatalytic activities compared to those with a rough surface and BET surface area above $50 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ (Table S3). The highest photocatalytic activity was measured for the heterostructure prepared from templates with the widest size distribution and the smallest average side length (Sample H4 in Fig. 5 and Table S3). SEM-backscattered (SEM-BSE) images (Fig. S12) revealed that the sample H4 predominantly consisted of entirely transformed

SrTiO_3 platelets ($L \leq 1 \mu\text{m}$) with a small content of larger heterostructural platelets ($1 \mu\text{m} < L \leq 3 \mu\text{m}$). Hence, the $\text{SrTiO}_3:\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ weight ratio of 1.3:1 (Table 1) does not represent the typical composition of individual platelets but reflects the average composition of the entire H4 sample.

To isolate the effect of the heterojunction, photocatalytic activities were compared for SrTiO_3 and heterostructural nanoplatelets, prepared from the same template and with similar surface roughness (BET values). SrTiO_3 nanoplatelets (Sample H3) and $\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ heterostructures (Sample H2) exhibited H_2 evolution rates of $1908 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and $2228 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, respectively, with comparable BET values (SrTiO_3 : $61 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, $\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$: $64 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$). The results suggest that a large surface area with more active sites plays a significantly more important role in activity than heterojunction formation alone.

Careful monitoring of the photocatalytic processes and a review of the literature can provide better insights into the plausible mechanisms behind the observed variations in activity. The main visual observation was that $\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ platelets turned black during the photocatalytic process (Fig. S13a), while the active SrTiO_3 platelets became brownish-greyish (Fig. S13c and d). However, after exposure to air,

Fig. 6. (a) Secondary electron (SE) and (b, c, d) backscattered electron (BSE) SEM micrographs of (a, b) as-prepared SrTiO₃/Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ platelets (Sample H2) and BSE micrographs of SrTiO₃/Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ platelets (c) after 4-hour photocatalytic H₂ evolution reaction (HER) and (d) after 4 cycles of 4-hour photocatalytic process. (e) Comparison of the XRD pattern of the as-prepared SrTiO₃/Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ platelets (bottom curve) with those after the 4-hour photocatalytic process (middle) and after 4 cycles of the 4-hour photocatalytic process (top). The XRD measurements were performed for the platelets cast on a single-crystalline Si sample holder. (f) Comparison of the Bi 4f XPS spectra of the as-prepared SrTiO₃/Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ platelets and after the 4-hour photocatalytic H₂ evolution (post HER).

SrTiO₃ nanoplatelets immediately lost their colouring. On the contrary, the heterostructure's intense black color remained stable and this was also confirmed by UV-VIS spectroscopy (Fig. S13b). SEM-secondary electron (SEM-SE) micrographs taken after a 4-hour photocatalytic process revealed no apparent morphological degradation in either sample type (Fig. 6a-d and Fig. 7a, b). According to XRD analysis, the photocatalytic process did not induce any structural changes to SrTiO₃. However, the disappearance of the Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ diffraction lines from the XRD pattern indicated a chemical transformation of the Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ component within the heterostructure (Fig. 6e). Post-reaction ex-situ XPS analysis of the active rough-surfaced heterostructures revealed a significant increase in metallic Bi⁰ (Fig. 6f), while Ti remained in the Ti⁴⁺ state (Fig. S14a).

The light-induced structural changes of the Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ part of the heterostructures were further investigated by STEM (Fig. 8). The thinned-to-electron transparency platelets were analysed in the edge-on orientation. HAADF-STEM disclosed severe deterioration of the Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ layered structure as shown by comparing SrTiO₃-Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ platelets before (Fig. 8a) and after H₂ evolution (Fig. 8b). Magnified images (Fig. 8c) show that previously single-crystal Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ composed of [Bi₂O₂]²⁺ layers and [Bi₂Ti₃O₁₀]²⁻ blocks, was replaced by the newly formed well-aligned crystallites, surrounded by the amorphous phase, whereas the SrTiO₃ platelets, epitaxially grown on both surfaces, appear to remain fairly intact. A heterostructural platelet with SrTiO₃ in [100] zone axis (see FFT in Fig. 8d) was investigated in more detail. In this orientation, the Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ would be oriented in [110] zone axis, with basal planes of Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ parallel to the (010) planes of SrTiO₃. A

combination of EDS analysis, HR STEM and Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analysis revealed that the crystallites are metallic Bi⁰ with rhombohedral crystal structure. The Bi particles crystallize as elongated grains with diameter of around 5–10 nm and lengths of tens of nanometres. Structural analysis of the Bi particles has shown that they follow two main orientations (Fig. 8e). In the first orientation, the (003) lattice planes are parallel to the basal planes of the (original) Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂, whereas in the second orientation, the (012) planes of Bi are parallel to the same set of planes. We assume that onset of recrystallization on the [Bi₂O₂]²⁺ sections of the Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ structure composed of double layer of Bi atoms would lead to formation of (003) lattice planes of Bi, whereas onset of recrystallization in the pseudoperovskite block would preferentially lead to the crystallization of (012) lattice planes of Bi and different orientation of the Bi grains (Fig. 8e) where the (012) planes of Bi are parallel to the basal planes of the original Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂.

The chemically bonded epitaxial heterostructures are generally more stable than physically bonded ones [5,30]. The particular instability of the Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ inner part of the heterostructures is associated with the well-documented ease of reducing bismuth-based compounds into metallic Bi⁰ by light and/or mild reductive atmosphere. Numerous studies have demonstrated the formation of Bi⁰ nanostructures through photoreduction, solvothermal/hydrothermal treatment or by chemical reduction of bismuth-containing salts, oxides, oxychlorides, etc. (Table S4, Table S5) [31]. In our heterostructures, Bi⁰ forms internally from Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ and is shielded above and below by SrTiO₃. Only the lateral parts were directly exposed to light and liquid. BSE imaging (Figs. 6 c, d) revealed decreasing central brightness with prolongation of

Fig. 7. (a, b) Secondary electron (SE) SEM micrographs of (a) as-prepared SrTiO₃ platelets (Sample H3) and (b) after 4 cycles of 4-hour photocatalytic process. (c) Comparison of the XRD pattern of the as-prepared SrTiO₃ platelets (bottom curve) with those after the 4-hour photocatalytic process (middle) and after 4 cycles of the 4-hour photocatalytic process (top). The XRD measurements were performed for the platelets cast on a single-crystalline Si sample holder. (d) Comparison of the Bi 4f XPS spectrum of the pristine SrTiO₃ platelets and after 4-hour photocatalytic H₂ evolution reaction (post HER).

the photocatalytic process, which implies gradual delamination of the forming Bi⁰ core from the SrTiO₃ part. Considering that the progressive Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ degradation did not cause any apparent interferences in photocatalytic performance across the four tested cycles (Fig. 5b), the exposed rough SrTiO₃ surface is most likely the main active region.

Such rough surface and porous morphological characteristics certainly play an important role in the photocatalytic activity, but it is unlikely to be the only determining factor. For example, in similar porous TiO₂ systems, other parameters, such as crystallinity, phase composition, fluorine in the TiO₂ lattice, Cu₂O co-catalysts, etc., also influence their photocatalytic performance [25–28]. Nonetheless, the formation of porous nanostructures could be an important design strategy for the enhancement of photocatalytic efficiency in TiO₂ and SrTiO₃ nanostructures.

The slight darkening of the active rough-surface SrTiO₃ nanoplatelets under light illumination (see Fig. S13 c and d) indicates light-induced reduction changes in these platelets. Ex-situ XPS analysis after the photocatalytic process confirmed that the greyish color of SrTiO₃ originated from an increase in Bi⁰, rather than from the reduction of Ti⁴⁺ to Ti³⁺ (see Fig. 7d and Fig. S14b). Since the morphology and spatial distribution of bismuth determine its role in the photocatalytic process, scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) was employed to examine the distribution of Bi within the rough SrTiO₃ platelets.

Fig. 9a shows a platelet that has been completely transformed into SrTiO₃ according to Procedure 2, resulting in platelets with a high surface area (rough surface). EDS mapping of a small area of this platelet reveals nanosized bismuth-enriched regions (Fig. 9c). Their distribution across the platelet is fairly homogeneous, and they are well-separated from each other. High-resolution HAADF-STEM analysis (Figs. 9d, e)

shows that Bi is present in clusters up to 10 nm in size, featuring aggregated Bi in the core and well-separated single Bi atoms at the periphery. Additionally, many Bi single atoms can be observed on the surface of the SrTiO₃ platelet as bright dots due to the high atomic number of Bi (Z = 83).

Considering that XPS analysis of the as-prepared rough SrTiO₃ nanoplatelets indicates the dominance of Bi³⁺ species, these isolated Bi atoms (including those in the clusters) arise from trapped Bi³⁺ ions coordinated with the oxygen anions of the perovskite lattice. The possibility that the cluster core also consists of trapped Bi₂O₃ nanoparticles cannot be excluded. For clarity and consistency, these bismuth-containing nanospecies are henceforth denoted as Bi single atoms/clusters. A comparison of active and non-active SrTiO₃ platelets in terms of EDS composition showed very similar amounts of bismuth (0.5 at. %) residues. Nevertheless, rough-surfaced SrTiO₃ platelets offer more accessible active sites, with a greater fraction of Bi exposed at the surface, in contrast to the smoother platelets where Bi residues are more likely to be embedded within solid SrTiO₃. Therefore, the improved activity of the platelets with a high surface area can be attributed to the increased surface availability of Bi single atoms/clusters, which are more likely to participate in the photocatalytic process (Figs. 9e, f).

These findings align well with previous reports, confirming the enhancement of the photocatalytic performances of semiconductors by their decoration with Bi⁰/Bi₂O₃ nanodots or Bi₂O₃ nanostructures (e.g. NO removal over Bi⁰/BiOCl [32], Bi⁰/g-C₃N₄ [33] and Bi⁰/TiO₂ (P25) [34], CO₂ reduction by Bi⁰/Bi₂O₃/TiO₂ [35] and by Bi³⁺/TiO₂ [36], phenol degradation by Bi⁰/BiOI-Bi₂O₃ [37] and NH₃ synthesis by Bi/BiFeO₃ [38], Bi/Bi₂Sn₂O₇ [39] and Bi/BaTiO₃ [40] (Table S4). Notably, the photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ to CO (E = -0.53 V vs NHE at pH =

Fig. 8. HAADF-STEM images of edge-on oriented SrTiO₃/Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ (STO/BIT) platelets: (a) as prepared and (b-d) after 4-hour photocatalytic H₂ evolution reaction. (c) Recrystallisation of single-crystal Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ to a composite material consisting of crystalline nanoparticles embedded in an amorphous matrix. (d) The crystalline grains are metallic Bi⁰ with two different orientations (1 and 2). (e) Schematic presentation of the transformation of oriented Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ to metallic Bi⁰ in two orientations.

7) requires even more negative potential than photocatalytic H₂ evolution ($2\text{H}^+ + 2\text{e}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2$ ($E = -0.41$ V vs NHE at pH = 7) [41]). Bi⁰ or Bi₂O₃ as a cocatalyst has also been reported to enhance photocatalytic H₂ evolution of several semiconductors, including TiO₂ [42–45], g-C₃N₄ [42,46], CdS [42], Bi₂O₂CO₂ [47], BiOCl [48], ZnIn₂S₄ [49] [50], N-doped porous C with Bi-MOF [51] and various direct Z/S-Scheme system such as Bi₅O₇I/Sn₃O₄ [52], Bi₂MoO₆/ZnIn₂S₄ [53], Bi₂WO₆/H-TiO₂ [54]. It was confirmed in several systems (Table S5) that the optimal amount of Bi, leading to remarkable improvement of the H₂ generation rates (14-times -108 times), is typically small in the range 0.25 % - 1 %. For example, Gao et al. observed a 106-times improvement of the H₂ evolution rate by in-situ photo-deposited 1 wt% (nominal concentration) of Bi⁰ on TiO₂ [42]. The actual content of bismuth determined by XPS was 0.2 at.%, which is comparable to the bismuth contents in our SrTiO₃ platelets. Similarly, Xu et al. [43], Reddy et al. [44] and Du et al. [45] reported 73-times, 5-times and 40.8-times improvement of H₂ evolution rates for different TiO₂ nanostructures loaded with Bi₂O₃ in the amount of 0.89 mol% Bi₂O₃, 0.5 wt% Bi, and 0.23 mol% Bi, respectively. The photocatalytic performances of as-prepared SrTiO₃ (1908 μmol g⁻¹ h⁻¹), SrTiO₃/Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ nanoplatelets (2950 μmol g⁻¹ h⁻¹), and SrTiO₃ nanoplatelets additionally loaded with Pt (3781 μmol g⁻¹ h⁻¹, Fig. S15) are comparable to other similar well-performing photocatalysts (Table S5). Several systems show much lower activity below 1000 μmol g⁻¹ h⁻¹, only N-doped porous carbon loaded with Bi nanoclusters obtained from Bi-MOF, stands out with a superior performance of 12,800 μmol g⁻¹ h⁻¹. The results, summarised in Table S5,

highlight the interest in designing photocatalysts by integrating non-noble metal bismuth with various semiconductors and studying their photocatalytic mechanisms and performances. Notably, since the H₂ evolution photocatalytic tests listed in Table S5 were performed in water/alcohol solutions, the Bi⁰/semiconductor systems demonstrate potential for H₂ evolution through simultaneous decomposition of organic compounds in the processes of so-called dual-functional photocatalysis [55,56] and photoreforming [57].

To obtain insight into the photocatalytic mechanism and charge transfer process in the studied SrTiO₃ nanoplatelets, photoelectrochemical (PEC) measurements and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) were performed (Fig. 10). The heterostructural SrTiO₃/Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ platelets were excluded from these studies because of their structural instability. Degradation of the internal Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ component under illumination might prevent reliable interpretation of the spectrochemical results. Linear sweep voltammetry (Fig. 10a) shows that all three SrTiO₃ samples are active for H₂ evolution but the catalytic rate of the sample C3 is much lower compared to samples C4 and H3. The trend in PEC performance is in line with the H₂ evolution rate observed in photocatalytic evaluation. Nyquist plots (Fig. 10b) obtained from the EIS measurements were fit with an equivalent electric circuit comprising two resistors, representing the solution resistance (R_{sol}) and interfacial charge-transfer resistance (R_{ct}) (Fig. S16 and Table S7). Sample H3 shows the lowest R_{ct} values, suggesting faster interfacial kinetics at the catalyst/electrolyte interface, which also explains its higher H₂ evolution rate. The circuit also contains two capacitors (C_s and

Fig. 9. (a) Bright field (BF) STEM top view of the part of the SrTiO₃ (STO) nanoplatelets and (b) Dark field (DF) STEM of the denoted magnified area in the interior part of the STO platelet, containing nano-sized bismuth species as shown by (c) EDS mapping. (d, e) High-resolution HAADF-STEM image showing Bi in the form of a nanocluster with around 7 nm in diameter and many individual Bi atoms (some indicated by arrows) on the surface of the platelet. (f) Schematic presentation of the rough platelets and are thus available for the photocatalytic reaction.

Fig. 10. (a) Cathodic linear polarization curves, (b) Nyquist plots obtained from EIS measurements and (c) Mott-Schottky plots measured at 1000 Hz for SrTiO₃ nanoplatelets (samples C3, C4 and H3) in 1 M KOH.

C_{dl}), corresponding to the capacitance due to the semiconducting catalyst (C_s) and the electric double layer formed at the catalyst/electrolyte interface (C_{dl}). It is notable that all the three catalysts show almost similar values for C_s , which is expected due to the same catalyst material. However, the value for C_{dl} is almost 12 times higher in H3 compared to C3 and C4. C_{dl} originates due to the interfacial interaction between the catalyst surface and the electrolyte, and a higher value is attributed to the high surface area of H3, which offers better percolation of the electrolyte into the catalyst surface, benefiting the surface redox activity. Mott-Schottky analysis (Fig. 10 c) revealed positive slopes for the SrTiO₃ platelets, confirming their n-type behaviour. The X-axis intercept of the extrapolated data gives flat-band potentials of -0.85 V, -0.89 V and -0.87 V vs. RHE for samples C3, C4 and H3, matching well

with the reported E_{CB} levels for SrTiO₃ (-0.80 V - -0.81 V) [7,58].

Band structure analysis is a prerequisite for understanding the photocatalytic mechanism. Considering that the measured optical band gap of SrTiO₃ is 3.26 eV, and its reported conduction band potential (E_{CB}) is -0.8 V, the valence band position is thus 2.46 V. The photoreduction of Bi³⁺ to Bi⁰ on the SrTiO₃ is thermodynamically feasible, as it is inferred from the more negative E_{CB} of SrTiO₃ compared to the reduction potential of Bi³⁺/Bi⁰ (0.308 V) [59]. This reaction is also supported by empirical evidence of Bi⁰ formation from Bi₂O₃ on the semiconductors with similarly negative E_{CB} (Tables S4 and S5).

The most plausible photocatalytic mechanism of the SrTiO₃ nanoplatelets with surface-trapped Bi single atoms, or clusters (Fig. S17), is similar to those reported for other n-type semiconductors decorated

with bismuth-based nanostructures [42,43]. Upon illumination with light of energy exceeding the band gap of SrTiO₃ (3.26 eV), electrons are excited from the valence band ($E_{VB} = 2.46$ V) to the conduction band ($E_{CB} = -0.8$ V), leaving behind holes in the valence band. The relatively less negative reduction potential of Bi³⁺/Bi⁰ (0.308 eV) makes the reduction of Bi³⁺ into Bi⁰ by the conduction band electrons of SrTiO₃ thermodynamically favourable. As a result, the photogenerated electrons reduce surface-anchored Bi³⁺ into metallic Bi⁰ (Fig. S17). Moreover, the Fermi level (E_f) of n-type SrTiO₃ (typically 0.1 eV–0.3 eV below E_{CB} minimum) is more negative than the Fermi level (E_f) of metallic Bi⁰ ($E_f = -0.17$ eV) [60]. This difference drives the electron transfer from SrTiO₃ to Bi⁰ till the Fermi levels equalise (Fig. S17). The resulting apparent equilibrium Fermi level (E_f^*) is more negative than that of metallic Bi⁰ and thus sufficient to enable H₂ production. Additionally, the formation of the Schottky barrier at the Bi⁰-SrTiO₃ interface leads to electron accumulation in the Bi⁰ sites, which then act as active centres for H₂ generation. Meanwhile, the photo-generated holes are expected to react with methanol, which acts as the hole scavenger.

4. Conclusions

This study enhances our understanding of the hydrothermal transformation of Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ Aurivillius phase platelets into 2D SrTiO₃ nanostructures, providing a pathway for rational control of SrTiO₃ surface roughness and functional properties.

By systematically varying the experimental parameters, such as the size of the Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ template nanoplatelets, strontium excess (Sr/Ti molar ratios = 12–15), and the temperature of the initial NaOH solution, we successfully synthesised both heterostructural SrTiO₃/Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ and pure SrTiO₃ nanoplatelets with varying surface roughness and exhibiting BET surface areas of 6 m²/g – 64 m²/g.

Smaller template sizes, higher strontium excess, and pre-treatment of initial platelets with warm NaOH promoted the formation of rougher, high-surface-area nanoplatelets. Photocatalytic hydrogen evolution showed higher correlation with surface morphology than with composition: smooth nanoplatelets (BET 12 m²/g) exhibited low activity (3 μmol·g⁻¹·h⁻¹–69 μmol·g⁻¹·h⁻¹), while the rougher structures (53 m²/g – 64 m²/g) showed much higher H₂ evolution rates (1908 μmol·g⁻¹·h⁻¹–2950 μmol·g⁻¹·h⁻¹) in neutral water/methanol solutions. Under light illumination, the SrTiO₃ part retained its chemical, structural, and morphological integrity, while the internal Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ part of the heterostructures transformed into metallic Bi⁰ and an amorphous phase, without impairing photocatalytic performance under tested conditions. This suggests that the heterojunction plays a minor role, highlighting SrTiO₃ as the main active component.

STEM analysis revealed a uniform distribution of Bi single atoms and clusters (~0.5 at. %) embedded within the rough SrTiO₃ surface. The metallic Bi⁰, formed mainly by in situ photoreduction of Bi³⁺ species, functions as a non-noble metal co-catalyst. Literature reports support the idea, that Bi⁰-containing systems are more suited for photo-redox processes, where H₂ evolution is coupled with oxidation of organics rather than for overall water splitting. This suggests that future studies should focus on dual-functional research, targeting reactions that yield value-added products or degrade pollutants in addition to producing H₂.

Finally, the demonstrated transformation from Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂ to 2D SrTiO₃ offers a template for engineering of other Bi₄Ti₃O₁₂-derived 2D ATiO₃ perovskites (A = Ba, Ca, Sr, Ba_{1-x}Sr_x) with high application potential in piezocatalysis, dual-functional photocatalysis, pyro catalysis, piezo-photocatalysis, photo-pyro catalysis, etc. Each system presents unique opportunities and challenges for controlling the structure-function relationship to achieve optimised performance.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marjeta Maček Kržmanc: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal

analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nina Daneu:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Khaja Mohaideen Kamal:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Blaž Likozar:** Writing – review & editing. **Alja Čontala:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Matjaž Spreitzer:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Jeffrey C.S. Wu:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Suraj Gupta:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.171758>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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